

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE CONCEPT OF "GOODNESS" IN THE LINGUISTIC LANDSCAPE OF THE WORLD AND ITS EXPRESSION IN DIFFERENT LANGUAGES

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqola keying yillarda lingvistikaning dolzarb mavzularidan biri bo'lgan olamning lisoniy manzarasining ifodalanishi haqida ma'lumotlar jamlangan. Shuningdek, konsept so'zining izohi va ezgulik konseptining ahamiyati yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Til vositalari, Lingvomadaniyatshunoslik, mifologik, diniy, falsafiy, lisoniy manzarasi, nospetsifik ranglar, "konsept", madaniyat konsept.

Аннотация: Данная статья содержит информацию о репрезентации языкового ландшафта мира, что является одной из актуальных тем языкознания в последние годы. Также разъясняется значение слова понятие и важность понятия добра.

Ключевые слова: языковые средства, языкознание, мифологический, религиозный, философский, языковой ландшафт, неспецифические цвета, «концепт», концепт культуры.

Abstract: This article contains information about the representation of the linguistic landscape of the world, which is one of the current topics of linguistics in recent years. Also, the explanation of the word concept and the importance of the concept of goodness are explained.

Keywords: Language tools, Linguistics, mythological, religious, philosophical, linguistic landscape, non-specific colors, "concept", culture concept.

It is known that today one of the most important topics in the science of linguistics is the study of the linguistic landscape of the world and its fragments, as well as spiritual and cultural concepts. There are also symbols of the linguistic landscape of the world understood through language - scientific and simple landscapes. These concepts are discussed below. The scientific view of the world is the most general system of ideas about existence, expressed by the fundamental concepts and principles of science. The main postulates of this science, i.e., the first rules and hypotheses are derived from these ideas. A simple view of the universe is a system of pre-scientific knowledge and ideas about existence that is used in everyday life. The concept of "linguistic landscape of the world" is firmly established in the treasury of linguistics and cultural studies, and the reference to it requires determining its interrelationship with the basic concept of "landscape of the world" related to the science of philosophy. Cultural scientists pay attention to the diversity of the world view, which depends on the subject, and the subject can be a person, a group of people, a certain nation, or humanity in general.

Many variants of the worldview depend on the social experience of a person. In other words, the wider the world of feeling (understanding, understanding, perception) that the observer is looking at, the more world views there are. Appropriate world views - mythological, religious, philosophical, and scientific views are the appropriate end of seeing the world [1]. If the idea of the diversity of the worldview was expressed relatively recently, the idea of the existence of a separate linguistic view of the world was expressed by V. von Humboldt at the beginning of the XIX century. It should be noted that the studies conducted on the linguistic landscape of the world, it is carried out in two directions. On the one hand, specific concepts related to this language, specific concepts related to

each language, or words representing non-specific colors are identified and described. On the other hand, studies are actively carried out about the meanings of conceptual concepts specific to a particular language, even if it is simple. These rules became the basis for studies that tried to describe fragments of a simple picture of the world. But the research of this or that fragment of the simple landscape of the world requires two dimensions - the selection of language material and its interpretation. In our opinion, it is justified in studying the concepts of "linguistic picture of the world" and "concept". Language plays a fundamental and active role in culture and perception. It is a unique feature that distinguishes a person from the rest of the world. Perception of the native language determines the natural way of acquiring it, a person acquires the native language from birth, together with the mother's milk. Also, language is the most important way of formation and existence of human knowledge about existence. In the process of activity, it reflects the objective existence and strengthens the results of human perception in words.

Objective knowledge of reality is complemented by the linguistic landscape of the world. The set of this knowledge reflected in the form of language consists of the concepts called "intermediate linguistic world", "reimagining the world in language", "linguistic model of the world", and "linguistic landscape of the world" in different concepts. Since this concept is widespread in linguistics, we choose the term "linguistic landscape of the world". The concept of "view of the world" (including the linguistic view of the world) is formed from the study of human perceptions of existence [2].

The joint interaction of a person and the environment, and the landscape of the universe is "the result of processing information about the environment and the person." In recent years, active studies have been carried out in the direction of studying the linguistic landscape of the world in linguistic and cultural studies. The concept of the worldview (including the linguistic view of the world) is

based on the study of human perceptions of the world. If the world is a relationship between a person and the environment, then the landscape of the world is the processed information about the environment and the person.

The concept is a derivative of the Latin word *conceptus*. The concept was put into scientific circulation in Russian linguistics in the first quarter of the XX century by the philosopher S. Askoldov. Until the 80s of the last century, this term was used as a synonym for the word *concept* in linguistics, but today it can be observed that its meaning has expanded considerably. The concept has a twofold nature. Because, on the one hand, culture enters the mental world of a person in the form of a concept, on the other hand, a person enters culture with the help of a concept and sometimes affects it. The concept was defined by the famous Russian linguist V.A. Maslova as follows: "it is a semantic structure in which the linguistic and cultural identity is recorded and describes the owners of a certain ethno-culture in one way or another." The linguist scientist N. Mahmudov in his treatise "Language system research" on the topic "In search of ways of perfect language research..." writes that "...the concept is a meaningful mental concept related to thinking, but it is quite controversial to consider it as a phenomenon completely devoid of national and cultural elements"[3].

The author of works on pragmalinguistics and cognitive linguistics, linguist Sh. In Safarov's words, "...a person learns language and the material world in the same way and in the same direction. The perception of the material world requires the creation of an understanding of the perceived object - events, and later this understanding is formed as a mental model - concept and receives a material name."

The concept is an actively used unit for both branches of modern linguistics, i.e. linguo-cognitology and linguo-culturology. We can see the analysis of the concept in the example of the following poetic text:

Oymomo oymomo,

A bowl was full of oil momo.

Maybe it's sugared

Sweet tea momo.

Oymomo oymomo,

Be happy, Mom.

Laugh at the good ones

Woe to the wicked[4].

(Anvar Abidjon)

The representatives of the Uzbek language through the concept of "Moon" in the cited poetic text

In his thinking, there are similes "with a moon face", and "with a beautiful face like the moon", as well as proverbs such as "The moon cannot be covered with a skirt". The "Go to the moon and return safely" unit is also used to share goodness with the person who has gone on a journey. In the above-mentioned poetic text, the concept of "moon" is also mentioned as a means of virtue.

In conclusion, it is worth noting that in recent years, active research has been carried out in the direction of studying the linguistic landscape of the world in linguistic and cultural studies. The concept of the worldview (including the linguistic view of the world) is based on the study of human perceptions of the world. If the world is an interaction with a person and the environment, then the landscape of the world is processed information about the environment and the person. It is known that culture is created by a person, a person, and he begins to live in it. It is in the person that the social nature of faith comes to the fore, and the person himself appears as a subject of social and cultural life. It is necessary to study the person from the perspective of the ethnos or the cultural tradition of the people because the cultural-anthropological prototype formed within the culture is necessary for the birth of a person in the human imagination.

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